
Breaking the Surface. Uncovering Mechanisms, Practices and Dynamics of Historical Engagement in the City of Cologne.

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Abstract

The development of municipal history and its foundations in the urban context of twentieth-century Germany is closely linked to institutions such as historical museums, archives, and local historical societies. In the city of Cologne, too, these institutions were established with the purpose of collecting, preserving and researching history. In doing so, they searched for a local identity and tried to define a specific heritage for the city of Cologne. This can also be seen as a response to the major social changes of the early 20th century, such as industrialisation and migration. The aim was to offer a local and unifying narrative alongside the formation of a national identity. However, the way in which history was presented and approached changed, especially in the second half of the 20th century: institutions opened up to new audiences, while at the same time the desire of citizens to participate in shaping history grew, as did the demand for a broader, more critical approach to the city's history (Jung 2013, 124-126, 158-159; Lenger 2014). New initiatives emerged, also in an attempt to address until then ignored or hidden perspectives or marginalized aspects of the past (Höpel 2017, 408-410, 412; Haumann and Schott 2021, 46-50). History in urban areas has long since ceased to be the domain of academic research institutions, museums, or archives. Although they are, and have often been, at the centre of public attention, the active shaping of urban history today involves a variety of actors (Ewen and Warwick 2021, 290-291; Minner 2019). History is "made" and told by established institutions in (semi-)professional settings, as well as by groups, associations, or individuals. However, the mechanisms underlying this "making" of the past remain largely unexplored.

This is where research project *DoingUrbanHistory. Practices of municipal history in the late 20th and early 21st century* comes in. It aims to identify the mechanisms and systematics in the processes of historiography, research, transfer, and communication of history in an urban setting from 1980 to 2022. The city of Cologne is the case study. The project also intends to examine changes in analogue and digital contexts, focusing on a diverse range of actors, including (non-)academics, civil society, politicians, cultural and economic figures. Three key indicators, namely 'doing', 'urban' and 'history', provide the structure for the primary research questions.

The primary focus for the first key indicator 'doing' lies on understanding how communication unfolds, identifying the mechanisms and (systematic) processes through which it occurs, and analysing these in detail. Particular attention is given to forms of action and interaction that can be discerned. This includes the identification of potential networks and

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connections, as well as the examination of both the self-perception and external perception of the various actors involved, and their understanding of what they consider worth telling.

In addressing the key indicator 'doing', for example, the project is based on the hypothesis that the communication of urban history is dynamic but characterised by specific path dependencies. It assumes a close link between historical storytelling and identity politics, as well as a transformative effect of digital media on interaction and participation, which has been significantly accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic.

With the key indicator 'urban' in mind, the aim is to investigate how Cologne's urban society adopts/incorporates history. This includes exploring whether there is a distinct urban society in the city of Cologne and, if so, how it defines its membership: who is considered a member, whose voices are heard, and who remains absent or silenced.

Focusing on 'history' as the final key indicator, the research explores who has shaped or influenced the course of history in Cologne within the broader context of the last two centuries – the chronological framework and reference of the project. It examines the changes and shifts that have occurred during the research period (1980-2022), taking into account the social, cultural and political demands of the time, with the aim of identifying concrete moments of transformation within the last 40 years.

In relation to the key indicator 'history', the project hypothesises that civil initiatives and associations play a significant role in shaping Cologne's local historical narratives, particularly in periods where established institutional frameworks were/are absent. The inclusion of diverse social groups contributes to a more pluralistic representation of urban history; however, it is hypothesised, that such narratives often remain within specific communities.

In order to capture the dynamics of 40 years of municipal history in Cologne, the research draws on a wide range of sources. The result is a complex data set that includes geodata (e. g. locations of institutions or events), text data (e. g. various publications, transcribed interviews), visual data (e. g. photographs, social media content) and network data (e. g. entities and their relationships, connections between institutions or communities).

Last winter, in cooperation with the City of Cologne, a survey on Cologne's historical initiatives was conducted. The dataset provides insights into the thematic focus, types of institutions, distribution of actors and different motivations regarding the shaping and communicating of history in urban space in Cologne. The survey also identified key contacts for subsequent in-depth interviews.

The contribution to HNR2025 is intended to provide an initial insight into precisely this dataset and how it, with the key indicators in mind, creates a spatial context within the city of Cologne. The survey already shows, for example, which spaces and locations in the city are particularly used by civic initiatives and associations today, and how these overlap with sites of institutionalised urban history communication and education. This allows for an exploratory analysis and categorisation with regard to local references from previous decades. In addition, the contribution aims to shed light on the thematic foci within the city and how these - consciously or unconsciously - repeatedly differentiate themselves from other themes, spaces and actors through their own specificities and characteristics.

From a public history perspective, a mixed methods approach integrating network analysis, mental mapping and qualitative content analysis allows for a comprehensive exploration of relational structures, frameworks and thematic patterns within the Cologne-based dataset. This approach enables the creation of visualisations within the research process, accessible to both academic and non-academic audiences (Shannon-Baker and Hilpert 2020, 51-54). These visualisations aim to demonstrate snapshots of time and the evolving dynamics of developments, actors and places.

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